

Excitation Energies of Canonical Nucleobases Computed by Multiconfigurational Perturbation Theories

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Abstract

In this computational work we assess the performance of *ab initio* multireference (MR) methods for the calculation of vertical excitation energies of five nucleobases: adenine, guanine, cytosine, thymine and uracil. In total we have studied 38 singlet and 30 triplet excited states. Where possible we used the multireference configuration interaction (MRCI) method as a reference for various flavors of multireference perturbation theory to second order. In particular we have benchmarked CASPT2, NEVPT2 and XMCQDPT2. For CASPT2 we have analyzed the single-state, multistate and extended multistate variants. In addition, we have assessed the effect of the IPEA shift. For NEVPT2 we have used the partially and the strongly contracted variants. Further, we have tested the commonly used RI-CC2, RI-ADC2, and EOM-CCSD methods. Generally, we observe the following trends for singlet excited states: NEVPT2 is the closest MR method to MRCISD+Q, closely followed by CASPT2 with the default IPEA shift. The same trend is observed for triplet states, although NEVPT2 and CASPT2-IPEA are getting nearer. Interestingly, the n, π^* singlet excited states were described more accurately than π, π^* excited states, while for triplet states the trend is inverted except for NEVPT2. The present work is an important benchmark for future photochemical investigations.

1 Introduction

The five canonical nucleobases (NBs) (adenine, cytosine, guanine, thymine, and uracil) (Figure 1) are the essential building blocks of DNA and RNA. They absorb UV radiation below

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21 300 nm, which can trigger a photochemical process that, eventually, can lead to structural dam-
22 age. Fortunately, the NBs have very high photostability due to efficient ultrafast radiationless
23 relaxation mechanisms to the ground state that prevents destructive photochemical reactions.¹
24 The manifestation of these protective mechanisms is found experimentally in ultrashort excited-
25 state lifetimes. To better understand these mechanisms, their photophysics and photochemistry
26 have been the subject of extensive theoretical studies that have been recently summarized in
27 a review.² The molecular basis of the photoprotection mechanisms, attributed to natural se-
28 lection and evolution,³ can be explained by the presence of conical intersections (CIs) that are
29 topological features of potential energy surfaces that allow radiationless decay. It is important
30 to emphasize that the existence of CIs does not guarantee that they will act as efficient mecha-
31 nisms for radiationless decay, but it is also necessary to investigate their accessibility from the
32 initially populated states to evaluate whether large energetic barriers connect the initial and
33 CIs structures along the potential energy hypersurfaces, which would make the CI inaccessible.
34 This intricate mechanism eliminates harmful photochemical processes that could lead to DNA
35 photolesions.

Figure 1: Canonical nucleobases investigated in this work. Visualization was realized using GV⁴ and POV-Ray.⁵

36 The accurate description of the photochemical pathway starts with the nucleobase being
37 excited from the ground state to an excited state potential energy surface (PES). Hence, a pre-
38 cise calculation of the relative position of the excited states and oscillator strengths is required
39 for understanding the primary photochemical events in this important class of biomolecules.
40 Therefore, the vertical excitation energies of the five nucleobases have been assessed for a broad
41 range of electronic structure methods.⁶⁻⁹ In addition, computational studies require the local-
42 ization of stationary points on the potential energy surfaces and the determination of relaxation
43 pathways connecting the critical points and passing through regions of degeneracy between sin-
44 glet states, or states of the same spin multiplicity in general, the so called conical intersections.
45 Recent studies suggest that also valence excited triplet states take part in the photochemical
46 mechanisms of NBs.¹⁰⁻¹² Therefore, the relative position of triplet states must be considered

47 as well in the calculations. In addition, intersystem crossings, regions of degeneracies between
48 states of different spin multiplicities (i.e. singlet and triplet state) are also involved in the
49 photochemistry. Hence, the description is highly demanding and requires quantum chemical
50 methods able to recover not only significant amounts of static and dynamic electron correlation,
51 but also to describe potential energy surfaces near degeneracies.¹³ These requirements are met
52 by multireference methods (MR). In contrast to single-reference methods (SR) that rely on a
53 single reference function, multireference methods are inherently more flexible as they are based
54 on a multiconfigurational wave function. These multiconfigurational methods allow a balanced
55 description of the valence excited states of different nature, e.g. π , π^* and n , π^* electronic states,
56 potential energy surfaces, state degeneracies and minimum energy paths connecting the most
57 relevant structures.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

58 Multireference methods can be divided into three major categories: (i) multireference per-
59 turbation theory (MRPT),¹⁷ (ii) multireference configuration interaction (MRCI)¹³ and (iii)
60 multireference coupled-cluster (MRCC)¹⁸ methods. Despite significant progress in method-
61 ological development^{19,20} and substantial hardware acceleration, the MRPT family of methods
62 including perturbation up to second-order (MRPT2) is dominating the computational pho-
63 tochemistry studies of NBs due to its accuracy at a favorable computational cost. A fourth
64 category was put forward by Li Manni *et al.*,²¹ who proposed to add some amount of density
65 functional correlation to the CASSCF²² (complete active-space self-consistent field) wave func-
66 tion. This method is called Multiconfiguration Pair-Density Functional Theory (MC-PDFT).
67 An alternative approach for combining CASSCF wave functions and DFT theory was pre-
68 sented recently by Hubert, Jensen, and Hedegård²³ (long-range CASSCF short-range DFT,
69 CAS-srDFT), with promising results for computing excitation energies of nucleobases. How-
70 ever, none of these recent methods is available in commonly available packages yet.

71 The Complete Active-Space Second-Order Perturbation Theory (CASPT2)^{22, 24-26} is the
72 most widely used MRPT2 method and considered as the most successful method for com-
73 puting excited state properties of medium to large system sizes, including nucleobases. The
74 so called CASPT2//CASSCF protocol has been applied successfully to investigate the pho-
75 tochemistry of canonical nucleobases and derivatives, as reviewed recently by several authors.²⁷⁻²⁹
76 The CASPT2 method is based on a zeroth-order CASSCF reference wave function. Examples
77 of the early applications of the CASPT2 method to investigate the spectroscopy of organic
78 (including nucleobases) and inorganic compounds are documented in the literature,^{26, 30, 31} from
79 which it becomes apparent that the accuracy of the computed excitation energies is 0.1–0.2 eV,
80 at a moderate computational cost. The original formulation of the CASPT2 theory (hereafter
81 called single-state CASPT2, SS-CASPT2) uses internally contracted configuration spaces span-
82 ning the first-order interaction space of the reference wave function exactly. The advantage is
83 that large CASSCF configuration expansions can be used as reference wave functions. The dis-
84 advantage is that internally contracted configurations are state-specific and introduce errors,
85 for instance, in the region of avoided crossings and when valence-Rydberg mixing occurs at the
86 CASSCF level. The solution proposed by Finley, Malmqvist, Roos and Serrano-Andrés³² to

87 deal with these problematic situations involves the coupling of several electronic states at second
88 order via an effective-Hamiltonian approach, known as the multistate (MS) CASPT2 method.
89 The presence of intruder states is another frequent problem encountered during CASPT2 cal-
90 culations, which is remedied with the imaginary level shift technique proposed by Forsberg and
91 Malmqvist.³³ Another drawback of the CASPT2 method is the unbalanced description of closed
92 shell systems in comparison to unpaired electrons.³⁴ To overcome this problem, Ghigo, Roos,
93 and Malmqvist³⁵ proposed a modified definition of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian employed in
94 the CASPT2 method, coined as the ionization potential electron affinity parameter (IPEA)
95 shift. The recommended value for the correction was optimized with a benchmark set of 49
96 diatomic molecules. The computations were done with the SS-CASPT2 variant, ANO-RCC
97 basis sets, and including scalar relativistic effects via the Douglas-Kroll Hamiltonian. Based
98 on the fitting of the benchmark against experimental quantities, they obtained a value of 0.25
99 Hartree for the shift. This IPEA shift (0.25 Hartree) became the default value even if the
100 studied molecule is very different from those included in the benchmark set. Recently, the
101 generalized use of this IPEA parameter has been questioned in several studies.³⁶⁻³⁸

102 The N-Electron Valence State Perturbation Theory (NEVPT), developed by Angeli, Cimi-
103 raglia, and collaborators,³⁹⁻⁴⁵ is another multiconfigurational perturbation theory based on a
104 zeroth-order CASSCF wave function. The main difference between the CASPT2 and NEVPT
105 is the choice of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian, which is the bielectronic Dyall Hamiltonian⁴⁶ in
106 the case of NEVPT. This choice of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian provides several advantages:
107 (i) it is size consistent and (ii) free from intruder states. Therefore, there are less parameters
108 and shifts to be used in comparison to the CASPT2 method. The second order NEVPT treat-
109 ment can recover the most relevant portion of the dynamic electron correlation effects and is
110 abbreviated by the NEVPT2 acronym.

111 Besides the approaches mentioned above, the XMCQDPT2 (Extended Multiconfiguration
112 Quasi-Degenerate Perturbation Theory) has been developed by Granovsky.⁴⁷ The XMCDQPT2
113 theory employs a zeroth-order Hamiltonian (H_0) invariant with respect to unitary transforma-
114 tion of the model space, in contrast to the one considered in the MS-CASPT2 theory. Due
115 to the choice of H_0 , the XMCQDPT2 is also invariant and the perturbations are taken as the
116 true two-particle operator. As proposed by Granovsky, the XMCQDPT2 is equivalent to the
117 MR-MP2 theory for a single-reference case, stable with respect to the model space, and does
118 not include artificially large off-diagonal elements, making it more efficient for the treatment
119 of conical intersections and avoided crossing regions than the above mentioned methods. In
120 XMCQDPT2, intruder state problems can be handled with the ISA (intruder state avoidance)
121 technique.⁴⁸ It is interesting to point out that with a proper selection of the shift parameter the
122 ISA and imaginary shift technique can be identical. Recently, this extension was adapted to
123 the CASPT2 approach by Shiozaki *et al.*⁴⁹ The resultant extended multistate (XMS) CASPT2
124 method was recently implemented in Molcas 8 by Dr. Per-Å. Malmqvist. The main difference of
125 the XMS-CASPT2 method with respect to the XMCQDPT method is the internal contraction,
126 preserving some of the later properties as, for instance, the invariance under unitary transfor-

127 mations of the model space; in this case, intruder states can be treated with the imaginary level
128 shift technique proposed by Forsberg and Malmqvist.³³

129 In addition to the well-established MRPT2 methods, there has been recent development
130 of new emerging approaches to add dynamic correlation effects to multiconfigurational wave
131 functions. Among them are: the Van Vleck perturbation theory,⁵⁰ the canonical transfor-
132 mation theory,^{51,52} the GASPT2 (Second Order Perturbation Theory for Generalized Active
133 Space Self-Consistent-Field Wave Functions),⁵³ the SplitGAS^{54,55} and new developments of
134 state-specific multireference perturbation theory.⁵⁶ In addition, efficient approximations have
135 been introduced to reduce the computational cost and provide favorable scalability, e.g. the
136 frozen natural orbital complete active space second-order perturbation theory method (FNO-
137 CASPT2)⁵⁷ and the domain based local pair natural orbital theory applied to the NEVPT2
138 method.⁵⁸

139 There is a growing interest in the assessment of multireference methods for an accurate
140 description of excited states energies in organic molecules, including DNA and RNA building
141 blocks. The work by Schreiber *et al.*⁶ has been considered as a reference work. In that pa-
142 per, the singlet and triplet excitation energies and one-electron properties of a set of organic
143 molecules were computed at CASPT2 level and a hierarchy of coupled cluster methods (CC2,
144 CCSD, and CC3). The most accurate method in this benchmark is CC3, an iterative Cou-
145 pled Cluster Approach including connected triples,⁵⁹ which was used as reference instead of
146 experimental values. The choice is motivated by the fact that most spectra are recorded in
147 solution, that different peaks might overlap and that vertical excitation energies do not corre-
148 spond to absorption maxima, making it difficult to directly compare experimental values to the
149 ones obtained with quantum chemical methods. However, the CC3 method is too expensive
150 for the calculation of nucleobases. Hence, the benchmark study by Schreiber *et al.*⁶ is based
151 on values obtained at the CASPT2 level, including only singlet states. Recently, one of the
152 present authors⁸ benchmarked the NEVPT2 method for the calculation of excitation energies
153 of the same set of molecules. However, it is not clear how the different MRPT2 compare
154 among themselves, because a reference value is missing. To resolve this problem we have used
155 internally-contracted multireference Configuration Interaction Singles and Doubles (MRCISD)
156 with the Davidson correction (+Q) as a reference, if feasible. The MRCISD+Q method is based
157 on the same reference wave function as the MRPT2 methods but is expected to be the most
158 accurate method in this work.⁶⁰ This makes it an ideal reference to assess which is the most
159 accurate MRPT2 method for nucleobases. The focus of our work is to compare the performance
160 of the above mentioned MRPT2 methods: SS-CASPT2 and MS-CASPT2 with and without
161 IPEA shift correction, XMS-CASPT2, NEVPT2 and XMCQDPT2 methods for the calculation
162 of vertical excitation energies and oscillator strengths of all five nucleobases. We have chosen
163 the nucleobases in their most relevant biological tautomeric form. To ensure compatibility we
164 employ the same geometry and basis sets in all cases, allowing us to derive our own set of
165 reference data, without resorting to experimental results. In addition, we have extended the
166 set of excitation energies by computing triplet excited states.

167 To complement the multireference methods, we have also computed the excitation energies
168 using accurate single reference methods that are frequently used in computational photochem-
169 istry studies. In particular, we have tested the second-order approximate coupled-cluster⁶¹
170 (CC2) and algebraic diagrammatic construction to second-order^{62,63} (ADC(2)) methods, owing
171 to high accuracy at low computational demand, which holds especially for their Resolution-
172 of-the-Identity (RI) variants RI-CC2^{64,65} and RI-ADC(2).⁶⁶ The results obtained with these
173 methods will therefore also be compared.

174 2 Methodology

175 All calculations in this work were carried out consistently with the benchmark reported by
176 Schreiber *et al.*,⁶ *i.e.* with the fully optimized contracted Gaussian basis sets of triple- ζ va-
177 lence quality (TZVP), developed by Schäfer, Horn, and Ahlrichs,⁶⁷ and geometries optimized
178 at MP2/6-31G* level of theory, frozen core orbitals. The geometry of guanine is missing in the
179 benchmark of Schreiber, therefore we have optimized it at the same level of theory employing
180 ORCA⁶⁸ software. The five nucleobases included in this work are in their most relevant bio-
181 logical form. The C_s point group symmetry was imposed in all calculations, computing each
182 multiplicity and symmetry block separately, for consistency with previous results;⁶ in the C_s
183 point group symmetry, the $\pi\pi^*$ states belong to the A' irreducible representation and the $n\pi^*$ to
184 the A'' irreducible representation. The CASSCF wave functions were computed employing the
185 state-average procedure for computing several states of the same spatial and spin symmetry
186 at the same time. The excitation energies for the n, π^* -type states were obtained using the
187 ground state energy computed with the same active space employed for the calculation of the
188 corresponding excited states.

189 2.1 Calculation of excitation energies

190 The singlet excitation energies were computed employing the same active space and number of
191 states reported by Schreiber *et al.*,⁶ but for guanine which was not considered in the original
192 work. That means, the active space encompasses all π and π^* orbitals, as well as the n orbitals,
193 including in the calculation a total of five $^1A'$ ($^1(\pi, \pi^*)$) and four $^1A''$ ($^1(n, \pi^*)$) states. As to the
194 triplet excited states, a total three $^3A'$ ($^3(\pi, \pi^*)$) and three $^3A''$ ($^3(n, \pi^*)$) excited states were
195 computed, with the same active space used for the calculations of the singlet excited states.
196 The employed active spaces for all nucleobases were visualized combining grid viewer (GV)⁴
197 and POV-Ray.⁵ Further details can be found in the corresponding sections.

198 Internally-contracted MRCI calculations⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ were carried out with the MOLPRO soft-
199 ware,^{72,73} with the default values. The relaxed Davidson correction is employed to obtain
200 the MRCISD+Q energies.⁷⁴ Note that MRCI calculations were performed for the pyrimidine
201 nucleobases only, because the active spaces employed for the purine nucleobases (adenine and
202 guanine) resulted in very large configuration interaction expansions.

203 CASPT2 excitation energies were computed for single-state (SS-CASPT2) and multistate

204 (MS-CASPT2) treatments, with and without the default IPEA (ionization potential - electron
205 affinity shift)³⁵ shift correction (0.25 and 0.00 Hartree, hereafter coined as IPEA(0.25) and
206 IPEA(0.00), respectively). Intruder states were treated with an imaginary level-shift correc-
207 tion³³ of 0.2 au. The use of the imaginary level shift is the recommended approach in Molcas.
208 However, in contrast Schreiber *et al.* employed the real level shift technique in the original
209 benchmark which might lead to small differences in the excitation energies between the origi-
210 nal benchmark and the present work. The extended multistate (XMS-CASPT2) calculations
211 were carried out without IPEA shift correction (IPEA = 0.00), but with an imaginary level
212 shift of 0.2 au. The CASPT2 calculations were done with the MOLCAS-8⁷⁵ software and the
213 XMS-CASPT2 calculations were carried out with a developers' version of the same program.

214 NEVPT2 calculations were done with the ORCA software.⁶⁸ Although different spatial
215 and/or spin symmetry blocks can be averaged with ORCA, they were computed separately, as
216 described above, to guarantee full compatibility with the results reported by Schreiber *et al.*⁶
217 and other results obtained in this contribution. It is also worth mentioning that the results
218 reported here based on ORCA calculations refer to the strongly contracted (SC) NEVPT2
219 variant;^{40,41} all calculations were done without truncation of the three- and four-body density
220 matrices (nef_d3tpre = 0.00 and nev_tpre = 0.00 options in ORCA). Doubly occupied and
221 virtual orbital energies in the Dyall Hamiltonian⁴⁶ were obtained with a state-specific Fock
222 operator (nev_canonstep 1 option in ORCA). Furthermore, the CASSCF energy and orbital
223 gradient convergence thresholds were set to 10^{-9} and 10^{-5} Hartree, respectively, and the aug-
224 mented Hessian Newton-Raphson step threshold set to 10^{-9} Hartree; as stated previously, the
225 NEVPT2 approach is free from intruder states problems, so no level-shift technique is required.
226 Also partially contracted (PC)-NEVPT2 excitation energies were computed employing MOL-
227 PRO. The lower degree of contraction should, in principle, yield more accurate energies than
228 the SC variant. To ensure consistency, we have compared the SC-NEVPT2 excitation energies
229 from MOLPRO and ORCA that were found to be identical. However, we have encountered
230 some difficulties for the calculation of the reference energy for the excitation energies of (n, π^*)
231 states. These calculations required the computation of the ground state energy with the same
232 active space employed for computing the energies of the (n, π^*) excited states, that is, with
233 the inclusion of n -type orbitals in the active space, which is difficult because their occupation
234 number was close to 2.0. For this purpose we have frozen one or two orbitals in the active space
235 in the MOLPRO calculations.

236 XMCQDPT2 energies were computed using FIREFLY software (version 8.0.1, build number
237 8540),⁷⁶ which is partially based on the GAMESS (US) source code.⁷⁷ In these calculations, the
238 intruder state avoidance (ISA) shift was set to 0.02 atomic units (au) to avoid intruder states.
239 The CASSCF step was carried out employing the graphical unitary group CSF (configuration
240 state function) approach, considering the calculation converged when the maximum permissible
241 asymmetry in the Lagrangian matrix was less than 1.0×10^{-5} au and the energy change smaller
242 than 1.0×10^{-8} atomic units. The XMCQDPT2 calculations were carried out employing the
243 recommended thresholds for numerical cutoffs. Inclusion of n -orbitals in the active space for the

244 ground state calculations lead to orbital rotation as reported above for the ORCA calculations.
 245 In order to obtain this energy, we have decided to approximate the state-specific solution with
 246 an extrapolation over a series of state-averaged solutions without using point group symmetry.
 247 For uracil, thymine, and cytosine the S_0 , S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 and for guanine the S_0 , S_6 , S_7 , and S_8
 248 states were initially taken with equal weights, and then the weights of the additional excited
 249 states were successively decreased by a factor of two. The series of the obtained CASSCF and
 250 XMCQDPT2 energies were quadratically extrapolated to a weight of zero for the excited states.
 251 In a similar manner, but with employing C_s point group symmetry, we obtained the energies
 252 for the three lowest lying ${}^3A''$ states of guanine, but only one additional state, *i.e.* $4^1(n\pi^*)$, was
 253 taken into account.

254 Linear-response RI-CC2^{61,64,65} and RI-ADC2^{62,63,66} calculations were done with the Turbo-
 255 mole software,^{78,79} with frozen core orbitals, and the default TZVP auxiliary basis sets. The
 256 SCF convergence criterion was set to 1.0×10^{-8} atomic units, otherwise default values were
 257 used. The reported excitation energies are in general agreement, *i.e.* ± 0.01 eV, with pre-
 258 viously published results for ADC(2) and CC2 calculations using different programs without
 259 RI-approximation, see Refs. [9] and [80], respectively. The only larger deviations are found for
 260 the ADC(2) calculations of the $4^1(n, \pi^*)$ states for uracil and thymine with deviations of 0.05
 261 and 0.06 eV, respectively. EOM-CCSD calculations were realized with Gaussian 09⁸¹ using the
 262 default values for convergence criteria. It is known that this method yields the same excitation
 263 energies as linear-response CCSD calculations, whereas differences in the oscillator strength
 264 between these methods exist.⁸² In the following, we only report the excited states of the single
 265 reference methods that mainly exhibit the right excitation character, *i.e.* π, π^* for A' symmetry
 266 and n, π^* for A'' .

267 Although multireference calculations can take advantage of computational procedures for
 268 speeding up integral calculations, as for instance the RI (resolution of identity) and Cholesky
 269 decomposition, they were not employed in this work. However, the effect of such approximations
 270 in multiconfigurational calculations carried out with MOLCAS can be verified in the results
 271 published in the literature,^{83,84} which indicate that in the case of Cholesky Decomposition⁸⁴
 272 with the default decomposition threshold (10^{-4} au) the mean error is about 0.001 eV, and
 273 smaller for larger basis sets.

274 2.2 Calculation of oscillator strengths

275 In general, the oscillator strength (f) in dipole form is given as:⁸⁵

$$f = \frac{2}{3} \Delta E_{ij} |\langle \psi_i | \mu | \psi_j \rangle|^2$$

276 This equation shows the two components of the oscillator strength: ΔE_{ij} is the excitation energy
 277 for a transition from state i to j in atomic units and $\langle \psi_i | \mu | \psi_j \rangle$ is the electronic transition
 278 dipole moment in the length representation. It is not possible for all methods to calculate the
 279 oscillator strength at the same level of theory as the excitation energies because the transition

280 densities might not be available, in particular for MRPT2 methods. Hence, in some cases the
281 oscillator strength is computed with excitation energies at one level of theory and transition
282 dipole moments at a lower level of theory.

283 For the SR methods CC2, ADC(2) and EOM-CCSD the oscillator strengths were computed
284 from all entities at the same level of theory. This also holds for the MRCISD calculations
285 in Molpro. However, the Davidson correction (+Q) is only applied to the energies and is
286 not affecting the wave function, hence it is not considered in the calculation of transition
287 densities. At the SS-CASPT2 level the oscillator strengths were computed with CASSCF
288 transition densities and the corresponding SS-CASPT2 excitation energies. The same procedure
289 is also applied to calculate NEVPT2 oscillator strengths. However, at the MS-CASPT2 level,
290 the oscillator strengths were obtained by combining the electronic transition dipole moments
291 computed with the perturbatively modified wave function and the MS-CASPT2 energies, using
292 the CAS state interaction (CASSI) method.⁸⁶ The XMS-CASPT2 as well as the XMCDPT2
293 oscillator strengths are computed following the same principle.

294 3 Results and Discussions

295 3.1 Excitation Energies

296 3.1.1 Uracil

297 The discussion starts with the uracil pyrimidine nucleobase. Its active space comprises all π -
298 orbitals, *i.e.* 10 electrons in 8 orbitals for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ excitations. In addition two occupied lone
299 pairs, n -orbitals, localized on the oxygen atoms are also taken into account for describing the
300 n, π^* states, resulting in an active space of 14 electrons in 10 orbitals (CAS(14,10)) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Uracil active space in terms of averaged valence natural orbitals. The active space was visualized using GV⁴ and POV-Ray.⁵

301 Uracil's excitation energies are listed in Table 1. Starting with the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, it is
302 observed that the relaxed Davidson correction leads to a lowering of the excitation energies
303 when going from MRCISD to MRCISD+Q. For the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, this correction increases
304 the excitation energies, whereas it decreases them again for both singlet and triplet n, π^* -type
305 states. In the following the MRCISD+Q values are taken as the reference value.

306 Strongly contracted NEVPT2 underestimates excitation energies for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, but

307 it is the best performing multireference method for this type of excitations. Surprisingly, the
 308 second best method is the partially contracted NEVPT2 with slightly lower excitation ener-
 309 gies. For the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, excitation energies are overestimated for both NEVPT2 methods
 310 and they perform rather similarly. In contrast, for the electronic states with n, π^* character,
 311 the results for the strongly contracted variant scatter around the reference values, so that the
 312 method does neither over- nor underestimate the excitation energies, whereas the partially con-
 313 tracted method underestimates excitation energies. Finally, the maximum absolute deviation of
 314 0.42 eV found with strongly contracted NEVPT2 for uracil is the smallest of all multireference
 315 methods.

316 Turning to the CASPT2 results, it is worth mentioning that the difference between single-
 317 and multistate calculations is relatively small with excitation energies differing less than 0.2 eV.
 318 However, the use of the IPEA shift leads to an upward shift of excitation energies of at least
 319 0.23 eV up to 0.63 eV. The IPEA(0.00) excitation energies are found to be too low for all types
 320 of excited states investigated and therefore the use of the IPEA-shift increases agreement with
 321 the reference value. In the case of $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, the IPEA(0.25) CASPT2 calculations scatter
 322 around the reference values, resulting in the most accurate results for these excited states. For
 323 the other excited states, *i.e.* $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$, $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and $^3(n, \pi^*)$, the excited state energies are still
 324 too low.

325 The performance of XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2 is close to each other. In the case of
 326 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, their excitation energies are similar to the IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 results with no
 327 clear trend and similar deviations from the reference values. The excitation energies for the
 328 $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states are systematically higher than for the IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 calculations and their
 329 deviations from the reference values are slightly smaller than for NEVPT2. However, for the
 330 electronic states with n, π^* character, the two methods severely underestimate the excitation
 331 energies by at least 0.62 eV and their mean absolute deviations of around 1.00 eV are the highest
 332 of all employed methods.

333 For the single-reference methods we find that EOM-CCSD yields excitation energies for
 334 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ and $^1(n, \pi^*)$ states that are the closest to the reference values and they scatter around
 335 them in both directions. The deviations of its excitation energies for the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states are
 336 similar to IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 underestimating excitation energies and for the $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states,
 337 the excitation energies scatter more strongly around the reference values than for strongly
 338 contracted NEVPT2, whereas the mean deviation is similar. For RI-CC2, the deviations for
 339 π, π^* excitation energies are smaller than for n, π^* . For the former, the differences to the
 340 reference are even slightly smaller than for strongly contracted NEVPT2, whereas for the latter,
 341 its performance is placed between IPEA(0.25) and IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 calculations. This
 342 trend of different performance for different transitions also holds for RI-ADC(2), whereas its
 343 general accuracy is lower than that observed with the RI-CC2 method. For $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$, $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and
 344 $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states, its performance is close to the IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 results; for $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ it is even
 345 slightly closer to the reference values than the IPEA(0.25) CASPT2 calculations. Note that
 346 the mean deviation of this method for the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states is similar to the ones for EOM-CCSD.

347 Overall and to sum up the discussion for uracil, NEVPT2 is the best performing multireference
348 method and there is a clear trend in accuracy for the single-reference methods: EOM-CCSD
349 > RI-CC2 > RI-ADC(2) with the exception of $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states for which EOM-CCSD performs
350 only as good as RI-ADC(2).

351 Regarding the state ordering, all methods agree that the lowest singlet state is of n, π^*
352 character, followed by a π, π^* -type bright state. However, the difference in energies for the
353 lowest excited state of both symmetries depends strongly on the method used for the cal-
354 culation and ranges from 0.1 eV for SS- and MS-CASPT2 without IPEA-shift to 0.85 eV for
355 XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2. For MRCISD+Q, this difference is 0.71 eV. It is best repro-
356 duced by XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2 for multireference methods and for single reference
357 methods by RI-ADC(2) followed by RI-CC2 and EOM-CCSD. For the other methods, *i.e.* SS-
358 and MS-CASPT2 with and without IPEA-shift and NEVPT2 in both variants, this difference is
359 underestimated. In addition, the lowest lying excited triplet state of both symmetries exhibits
360 excitation energies that are lower than the first bright transition for all methods employed, but
361 the energy difference also depends on the actual method. Therefore, the various benchmarked
362 methods agree in the ordering of the excited states, but energy differences between the states
363 vary strongly, which might influence the ultrafast deactivation mechanism.

Table 1: Vertical excitation energies ΔE (eV) for the lowest-lying excited states of uracil obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: five ${}^1A'$ (${}^1(\pi\pi^*)$), four ${}^1A''$ (${}^1(n, \pi^*)$), three ${}^3A'$ (${}^3(\pi\pi^*)$), and three ${}^3A''$ (${}^3(n\pi^*)$). Active spaces: A': CAS(10,8); A'': CAS(14,10).

	MRCISD	CASPT2											
		NEVPT2		IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)		XMCQDPT		ADC(2)			
		SC	PC	SS	MS	SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS	MS	CC2	CCSD
$2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.01	5.76	5.39	5.27	5.23	5.22	4.81	4.81	4.93	4.88	5.42	5.53	5.70
$3^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.85	6.65	6.33	6.22	6.17	6.15	5.72	5.71	5.80	5.62	6.27	6.44	6.76
$4^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.61	7.28	6.86	6.68	6.70	6.76	6.16	6.22	6.10	6.18	6.90	6.97	7.20
$5^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	8.37	8.01	7.64	7.38	7.33	7.43	6.70	6.83	6.82	6.76	7.41	7.66	7.81
$1^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	3.93	4.05	4.32	4.30	4.09	4.12	3.83	3.86	3.97	3.97	3.87	3.95	3.81
$2^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.61	5.67	5.87	5.83	5.60	5.61	5.17	5.18	5.36	5.36	5.35	5.46	5.39
$3^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.39	6.47	6.74	6.70	6.44	6.49	6.07	6.13	6.25	6.27	6.10	6.21	6.10
$1^1(n, \pi^*)$	5.18	5.05	5.10	5.04	4.93	4.91	4.70	4.66	4.08	4.43	4.65	4.92	5.12
$2^1(n, \pi^*)$	6.67	6.53	6.60	6.53	6.37	6.27	6.12	5.96	5.46	5.79	6.01	6.26	6.50
$3^1(n, \pi^*)$	7.80	7.42	7.00	6.82	6.97	7.01	6.58	6.68	6.18	6.25	6.60	6.73	7.68
$4^1(n, \pi^*)$	7.97	7.68	7.53	7.39	7.25	7.32	6.76	6.87	6.70	6.70	6.90	7.12	7.74
$1^3(n, \pi^*)$	4.87	4.82	4.91	4.87	4.74	4.73	4.50	4.48	4.20	4.46	4.43	4.68	4.85
$2^3(n, \pi^*)$	6.68	6.49	6.53	6.44	6.33	6.31	6.02	5.99	5.84	5.62	5.84	6.08	6.26
$3^3(n, \pi^*)$	7.61	7.42	7.32	7.22	7.11	7.14	6.66	6.71	6.11	6.67	6.55	6.67	7.58

364 **3.1.2 Thymine**

365 The replacement of uracil’s hydrogen that is bound to the carbon atom in position five of the
 366 ring by a methyl group, results in the thymine nucleobase. Its active space is similar to uracil,
 367 with one additional occupied π -orbital, *i.e.* 12 electrons in 9 orbitals for $\pi\pi^*$ and 16 electrons
 368 in 11 orbitals for $n\pi^*$ -transitions (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Thymine active space in terms of averaged valence natural orbitals. The active space was visualized using GV⁴ and POV-Ray.⁵

369 As can be seen in Table 2, its excitation energies are similar to uracil. In general, singlet
 370 and triplet excitation energies for n, π^* states are slightly higher compared to uracil, while
 371 the opposite is observed for the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, whereas no clear-cut trend is found for the
 372 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states. As for uracil, the Davidson correction for the MRCISD calculation leads to
 373 higher excitation energies for the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states and otherwise lowers them. Again, strongly
 374 contracted NEVPT2 is the best performing multireference method for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$, $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and
 375 $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states; the influence of the IPEA shift is larger than the use of single- or multistate
 376 CASPT2 calculations; IPEA(0.25) CASPT2 yields the smallest deviations for the $^3A'$ states;
 377 XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2 perform similarly by underestimating excitation energies for
 378 n, π^* states significantly; the accuracy of the single-reference methods decreases from EOM-
 379 CCSD over RI-CC2 to RI-ADC(2) with the exception of $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ for which RI-CC2 is the closest
 380 to the reference and EOM-CCSD and RI-ADC(2) perform about equally good. Also the state
 381 ordering is similar to uracil, *i.e.* the fact that a dark $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state lies below the first bright
 382 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ transition holds for most of the methods, with the exceptions of IPEA(0.00) MS- and
 383 SS-CASPT2 and partially-contracted NEVPT2 and that the lowest lying triplet state of both
 384 symmetries exhibits lower excitation energies than the first bright singlet transition. Overall,
 385 performance of the methods with regards to the MRCISD+Q reference and the ordering of the
 386 lowest energy states are comparable to that observed in uracil.

Table 2: Vertical excitation energies ΔE (eV) for the lowest-lying excited states of thymine obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: six $^1A'$ ($^1(\pi\pi^*)$), four $^1A''$ ($^1(n\pi^*)$), three $^3A'$ ($^3(\pi\pi^*)$), and three $^3A''$ ($^3(n\pi^*)$). Active spaces: A: CAS(12,9); A'': CAS(16,11).

	MRCISD	CASPT2												
		NEVPT2				IPEA(0.25)				IPEA(0.00)				
		+Q	SC	PC		SS	MS		SS	MS	XMS	XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2
$2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.00	5.71	5.18	5.05	5.07	5.06	5.06	4.64	4.66	4.88	4.76	5.30	5.39	5.60
$3^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.92	6.72	6.43	6.32	6.27	6.15	6.15	5.81	5.64	5.76	5.60	6.30	6.47	6.78
$4^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.56	7.20	6.64	6.44	6.51	6.55	6.55	5.97	6.01	6.01	5.99	6.72	6.80	7.05
$5^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	8.51	8.14	7.62	7.35	7.30	7.45	7.45	6.67	6.84	6.86	6.77	7.45	7.71	7.90
$6^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	9.12	8.99	8.68	8.56	8.44	8.61	8.61	7.75	8.01	8.25	8.16	8.70	8.76	9.09
$1^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	3.87	3.96	4.15	4.13	3.97	4.00	4.00	3.70	3.75	3.91	3.86	3.77	3.85	3.71
$2^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.62	5.67	5.81	5.76	5.56	5.58	5.58	5.16	5.18	5.38	5.35	5.34	5.45	5.37
$3^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.35	6.41	6.58	6.53	6.32	6.38	6.38	5.95	6.03	6.21	6.16	5.96	6.06	6.00
$1^1(n, \pi^*)$	5.24	5.12	5.15	5.08	4.97	4.95	4.95	4.75	4.71	4.13	4.49	4.68	4.94	5.15
$2^1(n, \pi^*)$	6.75	6.62	6.69	6.62	6.44	6.39	6.39	6.20	6.08	5.53	5.87	6.10	6.33	6.58
$3^1(n, \pi^*)$	7.81	7.42	7.01	6.81	6.93	6.88	6.88	6.55	6.50	6.23	6.25	6.59	6.73	7.68
$4^1(n, \pi^*)$	8.13	7.88	7.68	7.53	7.40	7.52	7.52	6.89	7.09	6.73	6.86	6.98	7.18	7.87
$1^3(n, \pi^*)$	4.92	4.87	4.96	4.92	4.78	4.77	4.77	4.54	4.53	4.25	4.53	4.45	4.70	4.87
$2^3(n, \pi^*)$	6.76	6.59	6.63	6.53	6.41	6.40	6.40	6.12	6.09	5.96	5.71	5.93	6.16	6.34
$3^3(n, \pi^*)$	7.77	7.60	7.51	7.40	7.27	7.29	7.29	6.82	6.86	6.21	6.84	6.53	6.66	6.64

387 3.1.3 Cytosine

388 Cytosine is related to uracil by substitution of the oxygen atom in position four with an amino
389 group and adding a double bond between the carbon atom connected to this group and another
390 nitrogen atom. It has the same number of double bonds and occupied π -orbitals as uracil
391 and, therefore, their π -systems have the same size (10 electrons in 8 orbitals) (Figure 4). For
392 describing the n, π^* excited states, the lone pairs belonging to the oxygen and nitrogen atoms
393 have to be taken into account resulting in an active space of 14 electrons in 10 orbitals, which
394 is the same size as the corresponding active space for uracil.

Figure 4: Cytosine active space in terms of averaged valence natural orbitals. The active space was visualized using GV⁴ and POV-Ray.⁵

395 The computed excitation energies for cytosine are displayed in Table 3. Going from the
396 MRCISD to the MRCISD+Q excitation energies, we observe that the different classes of cyto-
397 sine excited states exhibit the same trends reported previously for uracil and thymine. Also the
398 performance of various methods for the different classes of transitions follows roughly the same
399 general findings as for uracil and thymine. Strongly contracted NEVPT2 is the multireference
400 method for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states that performs best, but now it is similar to the IPEA(0.25)
401 CASPT2-calculations for the other states. The partially contracted NEVPT2 method is the
402 multireference approach closest to the MRCISD+Q reference for the triplet states of both
403 symmetries. The difference between single- and multistate CASPT2 calculations is still small
404 compared to the influence of the IPEA shift, but it is more pronounced for cytosine than for
405 uracil and thymine. The IPEA shift now alleviates the problem of the underestimated excita-
406 tion energies for the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$, $^1(n, \pi^*)$, and $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states leading to smaller deviations from the
407 reference values for the n, π^* transitions. However, excitation energies of IPEA(0.25) CASPT2
408 are still systematically too low for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states. The XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2
409 methods give results similar to each other, again, performing slightly better for π, π^* transi-
410 tions than the IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 methods, but significantly worse for the n, π^* transitions
411 underestimating these excitation energies by around 0.85 eV.

412 Referring to the single-reference methods, the same general trend in accuracy observed
413 previously is reproduced for cytosine. The EOM-CCSD method is the best performing single-
414 reference approach for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$, $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states; the RI-CC2 method is about

415 as accurate as strongly contracted NEVPT2 for the $\pi\pi^*$ transitions and is placed between
416 IPEA(0.25) and IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 for n, π^* excitation energies. As for the RI-ADC(2)
417 method, the deviations observed for the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and $^3(n, \pi^*)$ excitation energies are slightly
418 worse than those obtained with the IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 method, but better than those com-
419 puted with XMS-CASPT2/XMCQDPT2. Furthermore, the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ excitation energies are
420 similar to those obtained with the IPEA(0.25) CASPT2 approach, and the differences in ex-
421 citation energies for the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states fall in between those reported for the IPEA(0.25) and
422 IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 methods. Finally, the deviations of EOM-CCSD from the reference for
423 the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states are similar to the ones of RI-ADC(2).

424 For cytosine, the π, π^* electronic states have significantly lower excitation energies than for
425 uracil and thymine. Therefore, the corresponding lowest singlet state is now lower in energy
426 than the dark n, π^* state. As before the difference in energy between the two states depends
427 strongly on the quantum chemical method: the coupled cluster methods yield differences that
428 are too small and the multireference methods normally overestimate this value. Exceptions
429 are found for XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2, for which, due to the underestimation of the
430 energies for the n, π^* states, the differences are too small. Furthermore, the two lowest lying
431 $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states have now, in general, smaller excitation energies than the $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states, whereas
432 for uracil and thymine the first $^3(n, \pi^*)$ state has excitation energies lying between the two lowest
433 $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states. Finally, these two $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states are either below the excitation energy of the
434 first bright singlet transition or relatively close to it, so that they might be of importance for
435 deactivation via intersystem crossing.

Table 3: Vertical excitation energies ΔE (eV) for the lowest-lying excited states of cytosine obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: six ${}^1A'$ (${}^1(\pi\pi^*)$), two ${}^1A''$ (${}^1(n\pi^*)$), three ${}^3A'$ (${}^3(\pi\pi^*)$), and three ${}^3A''$ (${}^3(n\pi^*)$). Active spaces: A': CAS(10,8); A'': CAS(14,10).

	CASPT2													
	MRCISD			NEVPT2			IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)					
	+Q	SC	PC	SS	MS	SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS	XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
$2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	4.98	4.89	4.78	4.70	4.57	4.68	4.68	4.21	4.37	4.26	4.30	4.61	4.80	4.98
$3^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.11	5.95	5.74	5.65	5.58	5.52	5.52	5.11	5.02	5.31	5.09	5.57	5.71	5.95
$4^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.41	7.08	6.70	6.47	6.39	6.45	6.39	5.72	5.81	5.71	5.88	6.43	6.65	6.81
$5^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.62	7.35	6.98	6.83	6.83	7.01	6.83	6.20	6.45	6.63	6.35	6.88	6.94	7.24
$6^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	8.67	8.51	8.21	8.06	7.91	8.29	7.91	7.20	7.68	7.65	7.69	8.30	8.45	8.75
$1^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	3.86	3.97	4.18	4.16	3.96	4.04	3.96	3.66	3.73	3.70	3.82	3.81	3.93	3.84
$2^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	4.84	4.88	4.97	4.94	4.81	4.87	4.81	4.34	4.41	4.60	4.50	4.59	4.70	4.64
$3^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.54	5.54	5.47	5.42	5.31	5.51	5.31	4.82	5.12	5.27	5.18	5.26	5.36	5.26
$1^1(n, \pi^*)$	5.45	5.37	5.59	5.53	5.47	5.25	5.47	5.16	4.92	4.70	4.76	4.82	5.02	5.45
$2^1(n, \pi^*)$	5.76	5.70	5.83	5.77	5.48	5.70	5.48	5.18	5.43	5.08	5.13	5.25	5.44	6.00
$1^3(n, \pi^*)$	5.39	5.31	5.45	5.38	5.41	5.14	5.41	4.96	4.78	4.39	4.36	4.74	4.91	5.19
$2^3(n, \pi^*)$	5.61	5.50	5.67	5.63	5.30	5.50	5.30	5.09	5.19	4.72	5.07	5.05	5.24	5.76
$3^3(n, \pi^*)$	6.10	5.98	5.97	5.89	5.80	5.88	5.80	5.49	5.56	5.43	5.40	5.49	5.76	6.28

436 **3.1.4 Adenine**

437 Adenine and guanine have active spaces significantly larger than those needed for describing the
 438 pyrimidine derived nucleobases. To describe the π, π^* adenine excited states, we have employed
 439 an active space with all π and π^* electrons and orbitals, resulting in a total of 12 electrons in 10
 440 orbitals (Figure 5). As to the n, π^* electronic states, it is necessary to add the lone pairs from
 441 the three nitrogen atoms to the active space, which now contains 18 electrons in 13 orbitals.

Figure 5: Adenine active space in terms of averaged valence natural orbitals. The active space was visualized using GV⁴ and POV-Ray.⁵

442 The described active spaces proved too large for MRCISD calculations and therefore the
 443 discussion is based on comparing the results for the four types of excited states for the different
 444 quantum chemical methods against the results obtained with the strongly contracted NEVPT2
 445 method. Taking it as the reference, mean absolute deviations are in general lower than for the
 446 smaller nucleobases, mainly caused by the different choice of reference values. However, apart
 447 from that, similar conclusions are reached. Partially contracted NEVPT2 is rather close to the
 448 reference values, in particular for the triplets. For the CASPT2 results, one notices a higher
 449 impact on the excitation energies when the IPEA shift approach is used, than from variations
 450 between multi- or single-state calculations. The multistate formulation improves the agreement
 451 with the reference value (NEVPT2) by about 0.10 eV for π, π^* excitation energies, whereas the
 452 deviations for n, π^* states are independent of this choice. As before, XMS-CASPT2 and XMC-
 453 QDPT2 have mean absolute deviations for π, π^* excitation energies lying between IPEA(0.25)
 454 and IPEA(0.00) CASPT2, while the excitation energies for n, π^* states are underestimated.
 455 For the single-reference methods, RI-CC2 and EOM-CCSD show about the same deviations
 456 for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states. This is most likely caused by the change in the reference method as
 457 strongly contracted NEVPT2 systematically underestimates this kind of excitation energies for
 458 the pyrimidine-based nucleobases and the RI-CC2 excitation energies are always found to be
 459 lower than the EOM-CCSD ones for these states. For the other classes of states, the same or-
 460 dering in accuracy as before is found: EOM-CCSD > RI-CC2 > RI-ADC(2) with the exception
 461 of the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, for which EOM-CCSD is the worst performing single-reference method.

462 Overall, EOM-CCSD is the method which agrees the best with the reference for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$,
463 $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and $^3(n, \pi^*)$ states. RI-CC2 performs similarly for the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states and its deviations
464 are otherwise close to the IPEA(0.25) CASPT2 calculations. RI-ADC(2) has slightly larger
465 deviations for all kinds of excited states, with deviations closer to the IPEA(0.25) than to the
466 IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 calculations.

467 State ordering is similar to cytosine in the sense that the lowest singlet excited state is of
468 π, π^* character and in general two triplet states of the same symmetry are lower in energy than
469 this state. However, the difference in energy between the lowest excited state in each symmetry
470 is now smaller than in the case of cytosine and the first $^3(n, \pi^*)$ state lies either between the
471 two lowest $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states or is at least close to the second one.

Table 4: Vertical excitation energies ΔE (eV) for the lowest-lying excited states of adenine obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: seven ${}^1A'$ (${}^1(\pi\pi^*)$), four ${}^1A''$ (${}^1(n\pi^*)$), three ${}^3A'$ (${}^3(\pi\pi^*)$), and three ${}^3A''$ (${}^3(n\pi^*)$). Active spaces: A': CAS(12,10); A'': CAS(18,13).

	CASPT2														
	NEVPT2		IPEA(0.25)				IPEA(0.00)				ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD		
	SC	PC	SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS	XMCQDPT	SS	MS				XMS	XMCQDPT
$2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.22	5.08	5.19	5.21	4.71	4.74	4.79	4.81	4.81	4.79	4.81	4.81	5.20	5.29	5.36
$3^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.46	5.42	5.20	5.31	4.74	4.85	5.02	4.89	4.89	5.02	4.89	4.89	5.33	5.42	5.61
$4^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.68	6.48	6.46	6.45	5.81	5.84	6.16	5.89	5.89	6.16	5.89	5.89	6.50	6.58	6.83
$5^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.95	6.82	6.68	6.79	6.03	6.19	6.36	6.28	6.28	6.36	6.28	6.28	6.81	6.82	7.07
$6^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.01	6.92	6.73	6.92	6.20	6.33	6.61	6.33	6.33	6.61	6.33	6.33	6.87	6.93	7.17
$7^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.83	7.69	7.51	7.66	6.81	7.08	7.43	7.10	7.10	7.43	7.10	7.10	7.39	7.49	7.72
$1^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	4.28	4.26	4.08	4.15	3.74	3.79	4.01	3.91	3.91	4.01	3.91	3.91	4.05	4.09	3.90
$2^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.17	5.13	5.05	5.12	4.57	4.69	4.93	4.79	4.79	4.93	4.79	4.79	5.01	5.06	4.96
$3^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.64	5.61	5.42	5.53	4.98	5.13	5.37	5.30	5.30	5.37	5.30	5.30	5.35	5.42	5.22
$1^1(n, \pi^*)$	5.43	5.35	5.22	5.19	4.87	4.81	4.64	4.44	4.44	4.64	4.44	4.44	5.20	5.28	5.58
$2^1(n, \pi^*)$	6.16	6.07	5.94	5.96	5.62	5.65	5.40	5.21	5.21	5.40	5.21	5.21	5.84	5.92	6.19
$1^3(n, \pi^*)$	5.34	5.26	5.15	5.10	4.76	4.70	4.51	4.31	4.31	4.51	4.31	4.31	5.05	5.12	5.36
$2^3(n, \pi^*)$	5.77	5.70	5.61	5.64	5.27	5.32	5.06	4.90	4.90	5.06	4.90	4.90	5.56	5.63	5.80
$3^3(n, \pi^*)$	6.35	6.27	6.22	6.23	5.86	5.87	5.55	5.42	5.42	5.55	5.42	5.42	6.05	6.12	6.25

472 **3.1.5 Guanine**

473 In comparison to adenine, guanine has an even larger active space requiring 14 electrons dis-
 474 tributed in 11 orbitals for describing the π, π^* valence electronic states (Figure 6). As for
 475 adenine, three lone pairs have to be considered, being one for each of the two nitrogen atoms
 476 and one localized on the oxygen atom. So the active space comprises 20 electrons in 14 orbitals
 477 to study n, π^* electronic states.

Figure 6: Guanine active space in terms of averaged valence natural orbitals. The active space was visualized using GV⁴ and POV-Ray.⁵

478 The deviations of the methods from the SC-NEVPT2 reference exhibit similar trends as
 479 noted for adenine above. The largest difference in the trend is found for the RI-CC2 and RI-
 480 ADC(2) methods, specifically for states of n, π^* character. The former has now mean absolute
 481 deviations that are larger than for the IPEA(0.25) CASPT2 calculations, and the latter mean
 482 deviations that are even larger than the IPEA(0.00) CASPT2 calculations. But for the π, π^*
 483 excited states, both methods perform about as well as for adenine. Regarding the state ordering,
 484 as it was found for adenine, the lowest singlet transition has π, π^* character. Compared to
 485 adenine, the n, π^* states are higher in energy, so that the energy difference between the lowest
 486 $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state and the lowest $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ state is larger. As to the triplets, in all methods the two
 487 lowest lying states are of π, π^* nature.

Table 5: Vertical excitation energies ΔE (eV) for the lowest-lying excited states of guanine obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: five ${}^1A'$ (${}^1(\pi\pi^*)$), four ${}^1A''$ (${}^1(n\pi^*)$), three ${}^3A'$ (${}^3(\pi\pi^*)$), and three ${}^3A''$ (${}^3(n\pi^*)$). Active spaces: A': CAS(14,11); A'': CAS(20,14).

	CASPT2										
	NEVPT2		IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)						
	SC	PC	SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS	XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
$2 {}^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.14	5.03	4.91	5.01	4.50	4.58	4.53	4.57	5.05	5.18	5.29
$3 {}^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.98	5.85	5.73	5.48	5.20	4.85	5.23	5.11	5.59	5.67	5.90
$4 {}^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	6.87	6.76	6.48	6.69	5.92	6.16	6.36	6.23	6.65	6.69	6.88
$5 {}^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	7.20	7.03	6.95	7.32	6.20	6.74	6.96	6.68	7.17	7.22	7.50
$1 {}^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	4.54	4.48	4.35	4.40	4.01	4.07	3.98	4.19	4.30	4.41	4.26
$2 {}^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	4.59	4.56	4.39	4.47	4.02	4.11	4.50	4.23	4.45	4.50	4.37
$3 {}^3(\pi, \pi^*)$	5.55	5.50	5.29	5.41	4.84	5.01	5.21	5.25	5.38	5.46	5.27
$1 {}^1(n, \pi^*)$	5.72	5.67	5.50	5.49	5.27	5.25	4.86	4.99	5.28	5.56	5.65
$2 {}^1(n, \pi^*)$	6.73	6.63	6.72	6.44	6.37	6.06	5.67	5.60	6.27	6.42	6.73
$1 {}^3(n, \pi^*)$	5.48	5.44	5.33	5.32	5.09	5.07	4.78	4.92	5.04	5.30	5.36
$2 {}^3(n, \pi^*)$	6.25	6.15	6.20	6.20	5.92	5.92	5.28	5.01	6.01	6.07	6.11
$3 {}^3(n, \pi^*)$	6.94	6.86	6.75	6.76	6.42	6.43	6.08	5.23	6.23	6.38	6.80

488 4 Oscillator Strengths

489 The oscillator strengths computed at different levels of theory will be compared and discussed in
 490 this section. The excited state calculations were carried out using C_s symmetry, therefore there
 491 are no transition density matrices from $(n, \pi^*) \rightarrow (\pi\pi^*)$ states. For this reason the oscillator
 492 strengths cannot be computed for vertical excitations of this character.

493 The first vertical excitation of uracil has significant oscillator strength which means it is a
 494 spectroscopic state. Hence, the photoreaction path observed in uracil²⁸ starts from a lowest-
 495 lying $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ excited state ($2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$), the so-called bright state. As can be seen in Table 6 all
 496 methods considered in this study predict the existence of a low-lying $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ ($2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$) with
 497 large oscillator strength. The sequence of excited state ordered by the absorption intensity,
 498 as predicted by the oscillator strengths values, is the same for all computational methods:
 499 $5^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 2^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 4^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 3^1(\pi, \pi^*)$. NEVPT2 and CASPT2 are in general very
 500 close to the MRCISD values. However, we observe that for MS-CASPT2 the oscillator strength
 501 is increasing for states with small intensity at SS-CASPT2 level. While for the brightest state
 502 the MS-CASPT2 oscillator strength is significantly decreasing. The largest deviations from
 503 MRCISD reference are found for the XMS-CASPT2 method. Surprisingly the XMCQDPT2
 504 method is performing significantly better. The analysis of the single reference methods shows
 505 that the oscillator strengths for the lowest four states are good agreement with the reference
 506 values. However, the value for the highest excited state is strongly underestimated.

Table 6: Oscillator strengths for the electronic transitions from the ground-state to the lowest-
 lying $^1(\pi\pi^*)$ excited states (A' symmetry) of uracil, obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G*
 geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: five $^1A'$, active space: $^1A'$: CAS(10,8).

	CASPT2										
	MRCISD	NEVPT2	IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)		XMS	XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
			SS	MS	SS	MS					
$2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.214	0.210	0.204	0.325	0.187	0.310	0.361	0.274	0.233	0.197	0.236
$3^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.054	0.043	0.042	0.046	0.039	0.054	0.139	0.065	0.051	0.058	0.064
$4^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.180	0.197	0.192	0.254	0.177	0.249	0.205	0.224	0.206	0.187	0.220
$5^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.882	1.011	0.969	0.798	0.885	0.690	0.589	0.738	0.342	0.551	0.448

507 The computed oscillator strengths for thymine are displayed in Table 7. As expected,²⁸ the
 508 bright state, predicted at all levels of theory, is the lowest $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ excited state in the Franck-
 509 Condon region. The computed decreasing order of the oscillator strength is also the same for
 510 all MR methods: $5^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 2^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 4^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 3^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 6^1(\pi, \pi^*)$. However, for
 511 the SR methods the $6^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ state has higher oscillator strength than $2^1(\pi, \pi^*)$. In addition,
 512 RI-ADC(2) is severely underestimating the strength of the $5^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ excitation. Otherwise we
 513 observe the same trends for the methods as in the case of uracil.

514 Table 8 displays the oscillator strengths computed for cytosine. All methods predict that
 515 the $4^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ electronic state carries most of the intensity at the Franck-Condon region. The

Table 7: Oscillator strengths for the electronic transitions from the ground-state to the lowest-lying $^1(\pi\pi^*)$ excited states (A' symmetry) of thymine, obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: six $^1A'$, active space: $^1A'$: CAS(12,9).

	CASPT2										
	MRCISD	NEVPT2	IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)			XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
			SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS				
2 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.217	0.201	0.196	0.337	0.179	0.324	0.371	0.268	0.230	0.197	0.234
3 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.105	0.093	0.090	0.066	0.084	0.075	0.137	0.096	0.073	0.080	0.075
4 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.198	0.188	0.184	0.360	0.168	0.331	0.193	0.332	0.271	0.250	0.298
5 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.885	0.992	0.949	0.668	0.866	0.581	0.629	0.633	0.151	0.515	0.377
6 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.010	0.018	0.018	0.004	0.016	0.002	0.026	0.002	0.124	0.110	0.112

516 order of intensity for two lowest-lying $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states is reproduced for all the methods except
517 for XMS-CASPT2, where the first excited state is more intense than the second one. Also
518 the sixth state seems to be problematic. Only RI-CC2 can correctly reproduce the trend of
519 MRCISD.

Table 8: Oscillator strengths for the electronic transitions from the ground-state to the lowest-lying $^1(\pi\pi^*)$ excited states (A' symmetry) of cytosine, obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: six $^1A'$, active space: $^1A'$: CAS(10,8).

	CASPT2										
	MRCISD	NEVPT2	IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)			XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
			SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS				
2 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.059	0.068	0.065	0.093	0.060	0.097	0.130	0.075	0.047	0.049	0.063
3 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.140	0.087	0.085	0.360	0.077	0.383	0.035	0.316	0.185	0.165	0.185
4 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.882	1.082	1.030	0.633	0.923	0.513	0.806	0.576	0.659	0.630	0.641
5 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.183	0.057	0.055	0.352	0.050	0.330	0.252	0.316	0.088	0.168	0.168
6 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.193	0.279	0.269	0.134	0.245	0.104	0.246	0.137	0.222	0.223	0.087

520 Adenine is known to exhibit two low-lying electronic states of π, π^* nature,²⁸ the $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_a)$
521 and $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_b)$ states, the former being higher in energy and related to the electronic transition
522 bearing the largest intensity (oscillator strength). The relative energetic order of the $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_a)$
523 and $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_b)$ states in adenine is controversial; while *ab initio* methods predict the $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_b)$
524 state to be lower in energy than the $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_a)$ state, recent magnetic CD spectra assign the
525 inverse order ($L_b < L_a$), which is corroborated by TDDFT (time dependent density functional)
526 calculations.⁸⁷ The present study cannot be directly compared to the experiment because
527 the calculations are done in the gas phase, while the experiment is done in the solvent. The
528 solvation is expected to play an important role for the relative position of these two excited
529 states because of different dipole moments.

530 Since MRCISD calculations were not feasible we are using NEVPT2 oscillator strengths as
531 reference values, which doesn't mean these are the most accurate values. However, we observe

532 similar trends as in the case of pyrimidine NBs: (i) SS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2 values are
 533 the closest to NEVPT2 among all MRPT2 methods, (ii) the order of MS-CASPT2 values is
 534 inverted with respect to SS-CASPT2, (iii) XMS-CASPT2 performs significantly inferior than
 535 XMCQDPT2.

536 We observe that NEVPT2 and both SS-CASPT2 and the XMCQDPT2 methods yield sim-
 537 ilar oscillator strength. For these methods the first excited state has a high values, while the
 538 second one is almost zero. For MS and XMS-CASPT2 calculations as well as for the single-
 539 reference methods the second excited state has a higher oscillator strength. The difference
 540 between the single-state and multistate methods can be connected to the difficulty of these
 541 methods in the description of the two lowest-lying π, π^* states due to their energetic proximity
 542 (Table 4): when the calculation is done averaging of five singlet states, the lowest pair of π, π^*
 543 electronic states does not interact so strongly, as compared to the case of seven states, and the
 544 right order of the two transitions is obtained. The single reference methods predict the brightest
 545 state in agreement with NEVPT2, however, all the other states are in a different order.

Table 9: Oscillator strengths for the electronic transitions from the ground-state to the lowest-
 lying $^1(\pi\pi^*)$ excited states (A' symmetry) of adenine, obtained at the ground state MP2/6-
 31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: seven $^1A'$, active space: $^1A'$:
 CAS(12,10).

	CASPT2									
	NEVPT2	IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)			XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
		SS	MS	SS	MS	XMS				
2 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.269	0.267	0.159	0.242	0.106	0.044	0.269	0.081	0.037	0.003
3 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.001	0.001	0.190	0.001	0.220	0.310	0.061	0.243	0.276	0.315
4 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.380	0.367	0.547	0.331	0.479	0.010	0.479	0.545	0.496	0.552
5 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.213	0.204	0.003	0.184	0.019	0.328	0.009	0.042	0.004	0.029
6 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.003	0.003	0.008	0.002	0.006	0.152	0.003	0.036	0.085	0.074
7 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.054	0.052	0.037	0.047	0.029	0.063	0.029	0.249	0.319	0.312

546 It is a consensus that the bright state of guanine is the $^1(\pi, \pi^* L_a)$ state.²⁸ However, the
 547 second low-lying state of π, π^* character ($^1(\pi, \pi^* L_b)$) also has a large oscillator strength and
 548 can be populated at higher excitation energies. This trend, however, can be inverted in solution
 549 - the biologically relevant environment - as predicted experimentally⁸⁸ and theoretically.⁸⁹ As
 550 stated above for the case of adenine, a comparison of the calculated excitation energies to the
 551 measured absorption maxima is not possible.

552 However, we observe as a trend that all MR methods except XMCQDPT2 predict large
 553 oscillator strenghts for the two lowest-lying π, π^* states, and the correct decreasing order
 554 ($2 ^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 3 ^1(\pi, \pi^*)$). However, XMCQDPT2 and the single-reference methods have the or-
 555 der inverted for these two states. The trend for the higher lying states ($(4 ^1(\pi, \pi^*) > 3 ^1(\pi, \pi^*))$)
 556 is the same for all methods.

Table 10: Oscillator strengths for the electronic transitions from the ground-state to the lowest-lying $^1(\pi\pi^*)$ excited states (A' symmetry) of guanine, obtained at the ground state MP2/6-31G* geometry and TZVP basis sets. Highest root included: five $^1A'$, active space: $^1A'$: CAS(14,11).

	CASPT2						XMCQDPT	ADC(2)	CC2	CCSD
	IPEA(0.25)		IPEA(0.00)		XMS					
	NEVPT2	SS	MS	SS		MS				
2 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.219	0.209	0.262	0.192	0.293	0.289	0.157	0.203	0.178	0.185
3 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.133	0.127	0.211	0.115	0.151	0.077	0.302	0.349	0.337	0.372
4 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.023	0.022	0.008	0.020	0.006	0.006	0.003	0.032	0.026	0.032
5 $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$	0.225	0.218	0.064	0.194	0.030	0.119	0.050	0.416	0.392	0.357

5 Conclusion

We have presented a benchmark of MRPT2 methods for vertical excited state energies of five nucleobases. The present work is an important extension of the previous study of Schreiber *et al.* by: (i) guanine extension of the four nucleobases; (ii) providing a new reference for pyrimidines, MRCISD+Q, that is based on the same zeroth order wave function as the MRPT2 methods; (iii) complementing the set with triplet excitation energies; (iv) including new MRPT2 variants such as XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT2.

Among the MRPT2 methods we find the following trends: for singlets, the best agreement with the MRCISD+Q reference values is obtained for NEVPT2 and it is worth noting that the strongly contracted variant performs slightly better than the partially contracted one. CASPT2 calculations with the default IPEA shift follow closely. This trend is also observed for triplet states, but in this case NEVPT2 in both variants and CASPT2-IPEA exhibit nearly the same accuracy. Also the use of single- or multistate formulation does not have much influence on the excitation energies, but the latter method yields results a bit closer to the reference. In contrast, the use of the IPEA shift has the larger impact on the excitation energies: employing this shift, the excitation energies increase, ameliorating the underestimation of excitation energies found for CASPT2 calculations without this shift. For (π, π^*) electronic states (A' symmetry), the performance of XMS-CASPT2 and XMCQDPT is slightly better than CASPT2 without IPEA shift. However, among all MR methods these two methods are the farthest away from the chosen reference in the case of states with (n, π^*) character (A'') symmetry. Overall, the excited states of $^1(n, \pi^*)$ nature (A'' symmetry) were described more accurately than $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ states (A' symmetry), while for triplet states the trend is inverted except for NEVPT2.

In contrast, the SR methods exhibit smaller deviations from the reference for states of π, π^* -type (A' symmetry) compared to those of n, π^* nature (A''). The agreement with the reference increases from RI-ADC(2) to RI-CC2 to EOM-CCSD with the exception of the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states. For singlets, EOM-CCSD performs slightly better than NEVPT2, RI-CC2 similar to MS-CASPT2 with IPEA shift and the accuracy of RI-ADC(2) lies between CASPT2 calculations with and without IPEA-shift. For triplets, the accuracy of the SR methods decreases: the

585 deviations found for RI-ADC(2) are now close to the CASPT2 calculations without IPEA shift
586 and RI-CC2 exhibits errors lying between CASPT2 calculations with and without IPEA shift;
587 for EOM-CCSD its accuracy is close to RI-ADC(2) in case of $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states, whereas the $^3(n, \pi^*)$
588 states tend to be in similar good agreement with the reference as the excitation energies of the
589 singlet states.

590 As to the oscillator strengths, there are clear trends for MRPT2 methods. NEVPT2 and SS-
591 CASPT2 produce oscillator strengths that are close to the MRCISD reference values. There is a
592 deviation between single-state and multistate variants, the latter is found to underestimate the
593 oscillator strengths of the bright states and overestimate them for the dark states with respect
594 to the calculated intensities. For the single-reference methods we find a closer agreement to
595 MRCI, which is due to the transition densities being calculated at the same level of theory
596 as the excitation energies. In case of MRPT2 methods these transition densities come from
597 CASSCF calculations, which is less accurate. However, the order of bright states computed
598 with SR methods is inverted in some cases when these states are close in energy and have
599 comparable oscillator strengths.

600 We believe the present assessment of MRPT2 methods will serve as a reference in photo-
601 chemical studies of the five nucleobases. Further, it will be important for photochemical studies
602 of the reactivity that rely on an accurate description and the correct order of the excited state
603 in the Franck-Condon region.

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